

“A study on contemporary challenges of employee development in cooperative and public sector milk processing organizations in Western Maharashtra”

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Abstract:

Employee development responses, collected from 14 organizations management and employee respondents of cooperative and public sector milk processing organizations in Western Maharashtra, were judged on the basis of data presentation, analysis and interpretation and found that majority of the employee development practices were at below the standard level due to practical loopholes, and listed challenges of change and can be resolved by adopting scientific method of practice. This will help the cooperative and public sector milk processing organization in western Maharashtra to attain the desired level of employee development.

Key words

Cooperative, Public, Sector, HRD, Employee Development, Milk, Organization, Employee, Management

Introduction:

Employees have been considered as the soul of the organization because of their vital importance and underlined role played in the day to day business activity. Organizations worldwide are focusing more and more on employee development with the motto of 'the more the developed employee, the more their contribution to growth and development of the organization'. Employees including white collar and blue collar are focused under employee development processes. The father of the HRD movement in India stated about employee development as , "it is a continuous process by which employee of an organization are continuously helped in a planned way to acquire capabilities, knowledge, perspectives, attitudes, values and skill required to perform various tasks or function associated with their present or future expected roles; to develop their general enabling capabilities as individuals so that they are able to discover and utilize their own inner potential for their own or for the organizational development purposes and; to develop an organizational culture where superior subordinate relationship, team work and collaboration among different sub units are strong and contribute to organizational health, dynamism and pride among the employee"(**Rao, T. Venkateshwa, 1986**) . In order to enhancing competencies for senior manager roles, the Ex. Director IIMA and Management Consultant stated that, competencies related to contextual sensitivity, management of initiatives, introduction of innovations, resilience and effective coping through problem solving, effective task execution and interpersonal competences and leadership. [**Khandwalla, Pradip N, 2004**]. Out of the total HRD practices, the role of performance appraisal is very important because "Performance Appraisal is an Important Managerial Responsibility" and should be viewed as a beneficial process in HRD. It should be accepted as a normal management responsibility to review the performance of all employees and should also discuss its results with them regularly. The key elements of an effective performance appraisal system are - clearly defined performance standards, an effective monitoring system, regular discussion of performance, and development of appropriate action plans as a consequence of the appraisal. These elements will help employees to ensure, accept

and yield more desired benefits.'[*Simpson, Gordon L., Toronto Managing Partner of the Mansis Development Corporation,*]

So, in order to know the present level of employee development practices being followed and to bring required level of employee development in selected sectors milk processing organizations in Western Maharashtra for to help them to sustain in global completion, the present study focused on "A study on contemporary challenges of employee development in Cooperative and Public Sector milk processing organizations in western Maharashtra"

Methodology

In Western Maharashtra, among the registered organizations, 31 Cooperatives and 7 Public sector milk-processing organizations were actually functioning. Out of these, 8 organizations from Cooperative and 6 organizations from Public sector, in total, 14 organizations were incorporated in the sample of the present study. Proportionate convenience sampling technique was used to collect responses of 30% respondents of the selected organizations to accomplish the **objectives** of the study:

1. To know the present level of employee development practices being followed and
2. To suggest remedial measures, if required, for enhancement of effective HRD activities.

Researcher collected primary data through survey method, discussions and interviews, non-participatory observation method and secondary data through documentary research method and unstructured interviews.

Results and Discussions

The opinion of both the group respondents' regarding employee development activities in milk processing organizations of co-operative and public sectors in Western Maharashtra were collected through "Five – Point Likert Scale with No Opinion"

The highest possible Mean Score is '5.00' (100 %) indicates ideal position. *Mean scores above '4.5' (90.00%) indicate the respondents 'outstanding' rating of the HRD aspect; score between '4.5' and '4' (90.00-- 80.00%) indicate an 'excellent' opinion; '4' and '3.5' (80.00-- 70.00%) 'good'; '3.5' and '3' (70.00-- 60.00%) 'fair' opinion, implying that the particular HRD aspect may be improved through suitable methods and effort and between '3' and '2.5' (60.00-- 50.00%) 'poor' and 'Below 2.5' (Below 50.00%) 'very poor' opinion, indicating the need for a drastic intervention to bring about a change for the better.*

The employee development activities opinion survey data of Management and Employee respondents of cooperative and public sector of Western Maharashtra derived and presented in Table No.1.1. The mean score of co-operative and public sector employee development HRD activities were used for plotting the line graph and to study the contemporary challenges of employee development in both the sectors. Graphically it is presented in Graph No 1.1

Table 1.1- HRD Practices Opinion Survey of Management and Employee Respondents from Cooperative and Public Sector of Western Maharashtra:

HRD Practices	Cooperative Sector			Public Sector		
	Mgt. Resp.	Emp. Resp.	Mean Score	Mgt. Resp	Emp. Resp	Mean Score
1.HRD Concept	2.82	2.8	2.81	1.94	1.89	1.915
2.Role Analysis	2.9	2.9	2.9	2.08	2.26	2.17
3.Human ResourcePlanning	3.2	3.22	3.21	2.01	1.91	1.96
4.Recruitment	2.66	2.82	2.74	1.78	1.82	1.8
5.Selection	2.68	2.73	2.705	1.73	1.68	1.705
6.Placement	3.14	3.35	3.245	1.82	1.94	1.88
7. Induction orOrientation	2.53	2.38	2.455	2.74	2.21	2.475

8. Performance Appraisal	2.27	1.89	2.08	2.43	1.85	2.14
9. Career Planning and Development	2.2	2.33	2.265	2.04	1.91	1.975
10. Training	2.22	2.33	2.275	2.06	2.04	2.05
11. Development	2.81	2.93	2.87	2.24	2.15	2.195
12. Organisation Development & change	3.05	3.11	3.08	2.07	2.02	2.045
13. Workers participation in Mgmt.	2.66	2.84	2.75	2.54	2.57	2.555
14. Quality of Work life	3.31	3.46	3.385	3.7	3.49	3.595
15. Quality Circle	2.67	2.88	2.775	1.91	1.87	1.89
16. Employee Counseling	3.06	3.51	3.285	2.36	2.55	2.455
17. Team Management	3.31	3.41	3.36	2.46	2.42	2.44
18. Job Evaluation	2.35	2.39	2.37	2.13	2.12	2.125
19. Wages and Salary Admn.	2.95	3.04	2.995	3.14	3.17	3.155
20. Employee Benefits	3.46	3.7	3.58	3.33	3.38	3.355
21. Rewards	3.5	3.59	3.545	1.7	1.52	1.61
22. Grievance Procedure	3.15	3.24	3.195	2.4	2.39	2.395

Source: Primary data

Graph No 1.1 HRD Practices Opinion Surveys of Management and Employee Respondents from Cooperative and Public Sector of Western Maharashtra:

Findings & Conclusions:

On the basis of data presentation, analysis and interpretation and comparison of employee development activities Opinion Survey of Management and Employee Respondents from cooperative and public sector milk processing in western Maharashtra it was found that neither of the employee development HRD activities at 'outstanding' level nor at an 'excellent' level in both cooperative and public sector milk processing organizations in western Maharashtra; again, the Employee Benefits & Rewards practices were at good level in cooperative sector where as only Quality of Work life was at 'good' level in public sector;

Most of the practices such as, Human Resource Planning, Placement, Organization Development & change, Quality of Work life, Employee Counseling, Team Management & Grievance Procedure from cooperative sector and wages and salary administration & Employee Benefits from public sector were at 'fair' level, implying that the particular HRD aspect may be improved through suitable methods and effort and majority of the practices such as, HRD Concept, Role Analysis, Recruitment, Selection, Development, Workers participation in Mgmt., Quality Circle, Job Evaluation, Wages and Salary Admn. from cooperative sector and Workers participation in Mgmt. from public sector were at 'poor' level and Performance Appraisal, Career Planning and Development, Training & Job Evaluation from cooperative sector as well as almost all 18 practices as HRD Concept, Role Analysis, Human Resource Planning, Recruitment, Selection, Placement, Induction or Orientation, Performance Appraisal, Career Planning and Development, Training, Development, Organization Development & change, Quality Circle, Employee Counseling, Team Management, Job Evaluation, Rewards, & Grievance Procedure from public sector were at 'very poor' level, indicating the need for a drastic intervention to bring about a change for the better

Employee development practices loopholes and challenges in Cooperative sector milk processing organizations in Western Maharashtra:

1. Performance Appraisal
 - Non-scientific performance appraisal system
 - o Superiors favoritisms, prejudices and biases
 - o Political interference
 - o Irregular appraisal
 - o Non-involvement of employees in goal setting
 - o Non-potential appraisal
 - o Neglected IT in performance appraisal
 - and hence does not serve any meaningful purpose in more than half of both management and employee respondents performance appraisal.
2. Career planning and development, as an HRD practice, was very poor and inadequate to conduce personal development or career advancement of more than half of both the groups as it suffers from certain weakness, namely:
 - o Inadequate managerial expertise
 - o Weak support from top management
 - o Inadequate software and web based programme.
 - o Inadequate transfer, promotion and demotion practices
 - Obviously, this practice in co-operative milk processing organizations in Western Maharashtra needs to be renovated to meet the employees' expectations and to effectively deploy efficient manpower.
3. Training, as an HRD practice, was very poor due to:
 - o Poor awareness regarding training in co-operatives
 - o Brutal willpower of top management
 - o Very few on-the-job and off-the-job training
 - o Rudimentary evaluation programme
 - o Neglected e-training
4. Job evaluation as an HRD practice was very poor and inefficient to motivate to nearly half of the management and employee respondents, as it suffers from certain weakness, such as:
 - o Non-scientific job evaluation
 - o Lack of authorized job evaluation committee
 - o Neglected computerized system for evaluation
5. Grievance procedure, as an HRD practice, was very poor due to:
 - o Ineffective grievance procedure

- o Unaware to employees
 - o Seldom redress of grievance
- Hence, it needs to be changed drastically along scientific lines to serve its avowed purpose.
6. HRD concept was poor and inefficient to bring thorough development of both-organization and employees, as it suffers from certain weakness, namely:
 - o Lack of separate HRD department
 - o Inadequate awareness of HRD practices among workforce
 - o Inadequate HRD policy
 - o Lack of strong support from top management
 7. Like HRD concept, role analysis system in co-operative milk processing organizations in Western Maharashtra was due for reforms.
 8. Induction as an HRD practice was poor due to:
 - o Lack of arrangement of induction programme
 - o Ineffective arranged programm
 - o Little scientific approach
 9. Management Development, as an HRD practice, was poor and inadequate to conduce managerial development or career development, as it suffers from certain weakness, such as:
 - o Lack of political will power
 - o Rare arrangement of management development programme
 - o Inertness of top management
 10. Evidently, WPM in co-operative milk organizations in Western Maharashtra was quite rudimentary and does not fulfill its confirmed purpose

Employee development practices loopholes and challenges in Public sector milk processing organizations in Western Maharashtra:

Over all, Government of Maharashtra governs HRD practices, in public sector of Western Maharashtra, hence success or failure of HRD practices in this sector relates to the success or failure of policy decisions, rules and regulation of Government of Maharashtra.

1. HRD CONCEPT:
 - o Lack of separate HRM and HRD department
 - o Unawareness of workforce to HRD climate
 - o Lack of HRD policy
 - o Lack of top managements support
02. ROLE ANALYSIS:
 - o Weak design of employee's present and future role
 - o Poor experienced personnel
06. PLACEMENT:
 - o Lack of scientific approach
 - o Careless placement
 - o Rigid Government policy (due to the ban, placement on different jobs other than his own job)
08. PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL:
 - o Inconsistent performance appraisal
 - o Less impartial and objective study
 - o Absence of feedback and strength, weakness diagnosis of employees
 - o Poor performance standards
 - o Lack of involvement of employees in goal setting process

- Weak performance appraisal system
 - Absence of employees potential appraisal
 - Neglected use of IT in appraisal
- 09 CAREER PLANNING AND DEVELOPMENT:
- Poor transfer, promotion and demotion policy
 - Ambiguous career planning and development programme
 - Rare career planning and developmental programme
 - Scarce professional people to carry out programme
10. TRAINING:
- Insufficient training to cope with changing need of time
 - No scientific ness in training
 - Scarce on-the-job and off-the-job training
 - Absence of e- training
11. MANAGEMENT DEVELOPMENT:
- Poor practice of the programme for growth and development of manager
 - Hardly increase in performance of management groups
 - Poor practice of on-the-job and off-the-job technique
 - University tie-up programme
13. QUALITY CIRCLE:
- Employees unawareness
 - Rare implementation
 - Poor management support
15. TEAM MANAGEMENT:
- Ambiguous goal, policies and procedures
 - Poor team work environment
 - Poor face to face meeting of group members and shift leadership role to members
18. WORKERS PARTICIPATION IN MANAGEMENT: (WPM)
- Rare participation of employees in decision making process
 - No work committees at work place
 - No workers representative in joint councils
 - Poor faith on each other-management and employees
19. WAGES AND SALARY ADMINISTRATION:
- Fair level of existing wages and salary
 - Fairly sufficient to ensure reasonable standard of living
 - No linkage of wages and salary with productivity
 - No incentives for attaining targeted results

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